

GENRE AND STYLISTIC STANDARD OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *Translation is undoubtedly a very ancient form of human activity. In their work, a translator is constantly faced with the need to choose between different translation options, decide what is most important in the translated text and must be conveyed, and give preference to one or another method of overcoming emerging difficulties.*

Key words: *The importance of translating and interpreting, lexical, grammatical or stylistic phenomena, structural transformation.*

As soon as groups of people whose languages differed from each other were formed in the history of mankind, "bilinguals" also appeared, helping to communicate between "multi-lingual" collectives. With the advent of writing, such interpreters and interpreters were also joined by written translators who translated various texts of an official, religious and business nature.

Throughout the centuries-old history of translation, attempts have been repeatedly made to theoretically comprehend and explain the activities of translators, to formulate criteria for evaluating the quality of translations, and to identify factors that influence the course and outcome of the translation process.

In the course of its activity, the translator creates not just a text in the target language, but a text that will fully replace the original.

This means that the translator must be able to analyze speech segments in the

original and the units of the source language (s) that these segments consist of, find equivalent units in the NJ, build equivalent speech products from them, compare them with the original ones, and choose the final translation version.

Thus, the result of translation depends entirely on the skills and knowledge of the translator. Therefore, in our opinion, every translator should have an idea of the quality assessment of translation and its criteria.

An important role in achieving the adequacy of a translation is played by its genre and stylistic norm. It defines the necessary level of equivalence and, of course, the dominant function, ensuring which is the main task of the translator and the main criterion for evaluating the quality of his work. It should be emphasized here that just as the norms of correct speech can be established only taking into account the stylistic and sociolinguistic differentiation of the language, so the normative requirements for adequate translation make sense only in relation to a certain type of texts and certain conditions of translation activity.

Basically, the criticism of translations is based on an intuitive idea of the genre and stylistic norm. Translation of a work of fiction is evaluated according to its literary merits, technical translation-according to its terminological correctness, which provides an understanding of the essence of the matter and the possibility of using the translation text in technical practice, advertising translation - according to its validity, and so on.

Thus, from all the above, the genre-stylistic norm of translation can be defined as the requirement that the translation corresponds to the dominant function and stylistic features of the type of text to which the translation belongs. The choice of this type is determined by the nature of the original, and the stylistic requirements that the translation must meet are regulatory rules that characterize texts of a similar type in the target language. For example, the fact that a translation text is a technical description implies that it was the original description, and the language and style of the text is determined by the requirements for technical descriptions in the translating language.

In other words, the genre-stylistic norm of translation turns out to be twofold-oriented, and the most significant one is the orientation to the translating language.

The importance of translating and interpreting, lexical, grammatical or stylistic phenomena, structural transformation.

The activity of a translator involves knowledge of the system of correspondences between languages, techniques and methods of translation. All this indicates that every translator should be able to compare the translation text with the original, evaluate and classify possible errors, and make necessary corrections to ensure high quality of translation. To do this, you need to know what the translation norm is and the main types of regulatory requirements for translation.

The question of the norm of translation speech has been studied very little. The translation language must have certain features related to the specifics of this type of speech activity. The contact of two languages in the translation process inevitably leads to a wider use of similar forms, to the relative use of linguistic means.

The text of a translation is a speech work in the translating language, and of course it is bound by the rules of the norm and usage of this language. They vary both in different functional styles and depending on the type of general literary language. Among the latter, the language of colloquial speech and the language of fiction are usually bottled. In the linguistic literature, it was suggested that a special kind of language is also the language of science. The "secondary nature" of translated works and texts among other speech works in the same language.

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